

A Computational Design Algorithm for Manufacturing of Reinforced Structures with Wire Winding

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Abstract : in the article, the wire winding process for the reinforcement of a pressure vessel frame has been studied. Firstly, the importance of the wire winding method has been explained and literature was reviewed. The main step in the design process is the methodology axial force control. The frame consists of two columns and two semi-cylinders with circumstantial wires. A computational algorithm has been presented based on the governing equations and relations on stress-strain behavior of the whole system of the frame. Then a case study was studied to calculate the frame dimensions and wire winding procedure.

Keywords : Wire winding, Frame, stress, Design for Manufacturing.

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